

Accommodation over Rebellion: Modernity Redefined in Rama Mehta's *Inside the Haveli*

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Abstract

The novel presents an Indian interpretation of modernity and feminism. These western terms get a new meaning in the Indian context in this novel. Rama Mehta tries to preserve the Indian ethos and introduce fresh new ideas simultaneously. Geeta, the central character of her only novel, is presented as a woman negotiating the delicate balance between modernity and tradition, individuality and family, freedom and responsibility. She succeeds in finding some space for her, in turn, for modernity, within the four walls of the highly conventional haveli. She gently enters the haveli and blows the wind of change. Without causing any harm to the integrity of the family, she retains her individuality. Her endeavours to introduce radical ideas create upsurge and commotion in the haveli as well as in the Udaipur society. But they do not lead to any chaos or loss of harmony. This is the crux of the novel: being modern and enjoying freedom without causing disharmony.

Geeta does not hold the flag of feminism, liberalism or modernism. She does not fight for equality. The only thing she aspires for is the space for herself. And, she creates that without any loud revolt.

Rebellion is not an Indian way of getting things done in one's favour. Accommodation is more natural to us as it is a deeply-rooted tendency. Indian culture teaches and appreciates adaptability and flexibility of nature. By practicing them, one can move mountains.

Paper

Rama Mehta's only novel *Inside the Haveli* depicts the sincere efforts of a woman to create a room of her own inside the haveli. Geeta, the protagonist, is a modern educated woman. Liberal attitude of her parents, freedom provided by the culture of Bombay and education in co-education system have given her new ideas. She has developed broad mindedness and reasoning power, the chief characteristics of modernity. She is unaware of caste-distinctions, class-consciousness and the feudal system still existing in many parts of our country. She has no idea of the traditions strictly followed by the Rajput families of Rajasthan even today.

Marrying Ajay, she comes to Udaipur as a young bride of nineteen. She is welcome at the station by these words: "Where do you come from that you show your face to the world." (17) Pari, the head maid, informs her, "In Udaipur we keep purdah. Strange eyes must not see your beautiful face." (17) This is her first introduction to the life of purdah inside the haveli.

Geeta is observed suspiciously as she is 'an outsider' and that too, educated. People, especially women, are eager to know how she will adjust, "Everyone was waiting to find fault with her." (21) Her mother-in-law, by choosing Geeta as a wife for her only son, wants to show that even

an educated girl can be moulded into a submissive, ideal daughter-in-law. She gets involved in the rigorous routine of the haveli. She seldom speaks. She has to shake or nod her head demurely. The questions to her are answered by her mother-in-law. She does not like women gathering at the haveli. She feels depressed at the thought of women looking at her curiously and criticizing her bitterly. She feels nervous, embarrassed and humiliated at their comments. "No one thought her worthy of the family. Everyone was afraid she would embarrass them by an indiscreet word or a faulty move." (31)

Geeta greatly dislikes the rigidity with which the women hold on to old customs which do not stand the test of reason. What irks her most is the ill-defined nature of her role in the haveli. She is like a square peg in a round hole. She cannot become one with the haveli women, nor does she want to. She places herself on that border threshold of not belonging to either world. The world of men is forbidden to her and she is not at home in the world of women.

Geeta's persistent quest for intellectual freedom and choice-making contrasts significantly with the placid acceptance of the women of the havelis of their suffering as 'fate'. She thinks that it is criminal to accept everything as a part of one's predestined fate. She believes that one should at least try to change the unfavourable circumstances; one should fight for one's right.

Geeta has no suitable companion to share common interests, to spend time constructively or to engage herself meaningfully. She is kept away from any work or from any major or minor decision, of course, not out of malice but to keep her at ease. She craves for the company of Ajay. But according to the haveli traditions, they are not allowed to sit together and talk for long during the day time. She longs for privacy to read the books brought by Ajay or just to be with herself. But she is not allowed that also. She is all the time accompanied by one or the other woman.

She feels suffocated. She feels herself trapped in the haveli, with its unchanging patterns. She finds her life lonely and meaningless. Life becomes an ordeal for her. Her childlike enthusiasm and frankness disappear. She loses her confidence that "with love she could win over anyone, anywhere." (32) She thinks that she is a caged bird without wings. All her dreams and aspirations burn into ashes.

In the haveli of this novel, along with physical veiling, emotions must also be hidden. Geeta finds that although the other women thrive on gossip, they "never expressed an opinion and never revealed their feelings." (87) At times of extreme crisis, Geeta burns with rage, anger or frustration, yet remains silent. "Veiling the face is the overt symbolism of masking of inner emotion." (Grace 2003: 64) "In the haveli, no one really expressed their feelings. They covered their emotions in an elaborate exchange of formal gestures and words." (32) They are not supposed to show any special concern for their family members. Every emotion should be controlled. "Everyone moved cautiously; every word was weighed before it was spoken. Even with the servants no one lost their tempers." (33)

Geeta who is born, brought up and educated in the free and uninhibited world of Bombay is constrained to unlearn many things in order to confront the altogether different world of Udaipur. She is spontaneous, lively and has "not been taught to stint in giving affection, nor to keep her feelings concealed. In fact, her parents had encouraged her to speak her mind. But once she is in the haveli, her mother-in-law keeps reminding her of "the importance of reticence." (28) Her education begins anew and one of the first lessons she has to learn, with much pain and effort, is that to be a woman means to be in bondage of one kind or the other.

She learns another truth that defiance is detrimental and deference is rewarding. After some years, she also learns to control her emotions. Another drastic change is noticed in her attitude towards purdah. "She came to love the veil that hid her face, this allowed her to think while the others talked, ...through her thin muslin sari, she could see everyone and yet not be seen, by them." (23)

Geeta is not the type to cause disharmony in a family even if she personally feels frustrated. Again, while there are the traditional constraints upon her by way of certain customs, Geeta is not ill-treated by her in-laws. Indeed, politeness, formality and an underlying feeling of affection mark the relationship between Geeta and her in-laws. They make a conscious effort to come closer and try to understand, tolerate and appreciate each-other's views and needs. Contrary to her initial awe and fear of her parents-in-law, she finds gentle considerate concern in them. They display a rare flexibility and accommodativeness towards her. She also develops adaptability partly through her education and partly through the worm support of her family.

Geeta's father-in-law gives consent for Sita's schooling. Her mother-in-law, after hearing the bitter comments from the relative also, allows her to continue the classes. Geeta feels overwhelmed with admiration and gratitude for her in-laws. When people start criticizing the haveli for the classes held by Geeta, she is filled with remorse for acting impetuously without clearly thinking of the consequences. She has no desire to humiliate her in-laws or compromise the name of Jeewan Niwas. She does not want to inflict any pain on her ageing in-laws.

Geeta tries to assert her individuality by sending Sita, a servant child, to school. Here, in the absence of Kanwarani Sa, her mother-in-law, she is confronted directly to Pari. After the haughty encounter, she feels drained of energy. She feels trapped in the haveli with its unchanging patterns. But soon she realizes her mistake. She makes out that the other maid will resent her action. If these maids will stop attending Sita, Geeta cannot replace their attention and love for Sita.

Then, she starts classes for women and the poor children. She wants to fight their ignorance and superstition. But the women of the other havelis accuse Geeta of giving fancy ideas to the poor and the illiterate. Women themselves criticize the idea of educating girls with the fear of not finding an educated groom for them and with the fear of losing servility of the servant women. Geeta feels deep remorse for bringing bad name to the haveli.

But, once again, her father-in-law supports her. He and Ajay feel proud of her. They wholeheartedly welcome the changes brought by Geeta. They encourage her to utilize her education. They accept her efforts to assert her individuality. They see Geeta suffocated by the haveli traditions. They try their best to make her feel comfortable in the haveli.

Ajay has been a worm support for Geeta throughout the novel. He understands her state of mind. Geeta is a companion to him. He brings various books for her. They discuss on many topics. When he sees her desperate and furious, he tries to pacify her. He knows that the life in purdah is not meant for her. He promises to support her in whatever she decides to do. He approves Geeta's bold step of sending Sita to school: "It is time for new ideas to enter the haveli." (137) He asks her to be calm and patient. "...by being depressed, you will not change things." (52) He is grateful to Geeta for accommodating herself in the haveli and in Udaipur. Otherwise, he would never have been content in Udaipur. When he makes it clear to her that he is not going to leave Udaipur, Geeta defiantly retorts at him. But then, she is relieved as the uncertainty is now over. "A few words had put an end to her restlessness." (138)

Geeta bitterly argues with Ajay over the issue of their daughter Vijay's engagement. She accuses him and his family of giving more importance to prestige and money. But Ajay does not get angry. He assures her for not allowing any such thing to happen. He proposes her to go for a long ride. But Geeta is afraid of the criticism. Ajay says, "As long as I am with you, no one dare lift a finger against you." (208) Geeta knows very well that Ajay's assurances to her are not mere words. The strength she gets from him is real.

Geeta's conjugal relationship with Ajay is quite satisfactory. Geeta has a complaint against Ajay for the special treatment he gets in the haveli being a man. She does not like Ajay giving priority and importance to the haveli and the wish of his parents. But their personal relationship is soundly based on the love and trust they share. Both of them respect each other's feelings. They argue on various matters, but never hurt or humiliate each other. Ajay does not exhibit any kind of superiority. And Geeta always talks on equal friendly terms with Ajay. A sign of healthy relationship is seen in Geeta's acceptance of Ajay's decision of not leaving Udaipur. Ajay strengthens the relationship by giving sufficient space to Geeta with all her modernity. Geeta's compliance with the traditions of the haveli meets an acid test in the final section of the novel. Her approval of child-marriage for Vijay is the ultimate test of her professed loyalty to the haveli. The decision she is asked to make shakes her to the core. She bursts out in anger. A haughty discussion with Ajay follows. In this moment of passion, Geeta, despite her noble sentiments about Jeewan Niwas, separates herself from the people of the havelis. With the mask of courtesy undone, Geeta reveals how much she still retains of the outsider's perspective on haveli culture and to what degree those who are within the threshold view her education as a threat to traditional continuities.

The issue of Vijay's engagement produces the bitterest reactions in Geeta. She retorts at Kanwarani Sa and furiously argues with Ajay over the matter. Afterwards she is compelled to give a second thought to the proposal. She meets Vir Singh, the suitor for Vijay, and can find no guilt with him. He is a perfect match for Vijay. On the other hand, the ill father-in-law talks to Geeta about the proposal. His practical thoughts inspire Geeta to reconsider the matter. Geeta's final decision is not declared by the novelist. But the reader can guess it. Her approach so far drags her towards the traditional option.

There are moments of obvious revolt; sometimes of suppressed seething indignation, at other times angry outbursts. But these expressions of revolt are only addressed to a loving Husband and a loyal maid. "Her response follows the same pattern outright -- vehement rejection, followed by confusion and re-consideration, culminating in acceptance." (Roy 1999: 120)

Every society creates its own particular attitudinal patterns. The head-on confrontation with unacceptable social mores is a common path towards individuation in the West. But this kind of staunch feminist fervor is less feasible in the Indian context. One cannot afford to be a revolutionary in the classic feminist sense — loud, confrontational or assertively radical. Here, the most natural and widely adopted strategy of resolution is that of accommodation and compromise. Geeta demonstrates her open-mindedness by respecting the haveli traditions. She basically does not aim to destroy anything. She just aims to create space for fresh new ideas and practices. She does not try for absolute freedom; rather, she consciously embraces freedom with a great sense of responsibility.

The dichotomy between the traditional values and the urge towards individual self-fulfillment that marks modernity can often lead to a titanic clash. Rejection of these values will take away

something of great human worth from our social system but an uncritical prolongation can lead to a suffocation of an individual's sense of self. The most viable solution lies in a conscious, voluntary accommodation and adjustment. "Growth does not necessarily call for a rejection of the past in toto but a selective retention of that which has value combined with a critical assimilation of the positive attributes of the present." (Roy 1999: 101)

Hailing from a liberal family background, Geeta is subject to a severe culture shock on her initiation into life in purdah. At this critical juncture, she has three choices -- to openly rebel, to surrender totally or to work out an honorable compromise. Her attempts to create a space for herself by starting classes for the maid servants and their children can be categorized as a constructive attempt to modify the life in the haveli. All those who initially oppose her are shown to be radically changing their stance. Geeta, too, gains tremendously through her endeavours. Her empty hours fruitfully occupied; she now looks forward to every morning; she "no longer felt trapped in the haveli". (142) Symbolically, the cobwebs which hung in the large empty rooms had been cleared by the boys. Geeta's attempt to accommodate the restricted life of the haveli with the benefits of modern education has also been acclaimed by many critics. Santosh Gupta comments: "The harmonious relationship that Geeta builds up inside the haveli, without either surrendering her own intellectual independence or disrupting traditions, reflects her ability to use her education in a creative manner." (1991: 227) Geeta's resolution to her dilemma is thus seen as an appreciable constructive accommodation, an acceptable strategy on feminist terms.

The fact that Geeta eventually accepts the discipline of the haveli without protest highlights the possibility of choice within the traditional forms of seclusion. As Nussbaum (2000: 236) argues, an informed choice to continue traditional modes of behaviour can be viewed as a statement of freedom equivalent to a rejection of purdah. The solutions to Geeta's problems "are not easy to come, nor are they available made to order. They succeed severe trials and tribulations, restrictions, continence, humiliations, constricting manners, mores and taboos. Traditionally, this is *Sadhana*. Even the slightest swerving from the balance, any immature waywardness any desperate and defiant deed is sure to land one in interminable trouble, as is testified by the case of Lakshmi." (Chindhade 1991: 10)

Geeta becomes an agent of change. She comes to the threshold and opens the door for the fresh air to enter the haveli. Without putting a step across the threshold, she manages to bring a world of new ideas to the haveli. In the process of being moulded by the haveli into its traditional image, Geeta moulds the haveli in such a way that it accepts the modern ways very naturally. K. R. S. Iyengar opines: "...although Geeta gradually gets used to its life changing herself in the process, she also subtly changes her immediate environment and the people concerned." (2008: 752)

Geeta's perseverance is justly rewarded. After spending many years as 'an outsider' in the haveli, she becomes the 'mistress'. Her strategy is negotiation, not transmutation. She adopts the pattern of compromise instead of that of rebellion. She displays her ability to locate her resources and gets a positive response from her elders in adverse conditions. She is a unique blend of tradition and modernity. She successfully keeps away from both the extremes. She chooses a moderate path ('Madhyam Marg' -- an Indian ideal for happy life). She accepts traditions without either disrupting the harmony of the life in haveli or violating her own basic integrity. Retaining her own identity, she becomes an inevitable part of the milieu. Nandu Bua sa comments: "...who could say you were not one of us? You have become a real Rajasthani." (113)

The journey of Geeta's life begins with frustration and ends with complete realization of the values of life. The novel begins with questions regarding the ancient tradition and ends with convincing solution about the meaning of tradition. Geeta enters the haveli, confront the traditions, accepts them, internalizes them gradually and in turn creates space for modernity. She patiently turns the circumstances in favour of her new ideas so that she can easily introduce them without any disturbance. She preserves her own voice within the given social framework. "The provincial story of Udaipur transforms into the story of every Indian woman who tries to establish the bridge between traditional and modern values of life. Geeta understands that salvation does not lie always in breaking away but rather in getting within tradition with a comfortable space of one's own thus achieving a complete, wholistic, harmonious existence." (Trivedi 2004: 129-130) Though Geeta brings transformation in the life of the haveli, she must undergo her own 'regressive' transformation from the 'modern' to the 'ancient', before she can function effectively. This reflects the Indian mode of feminist negotiation emphasizing accommodation, relational harmony and non-confrontational assertion.

Geeta's modernity is the result of positive and constructive effect of her education. Education cultivates tolerance, open-mindedness, understanding and maturity. It broadens her outlook. She accepts and respects other's views. She does not believe in any kind of class, gender, caste or religion distinctions. She talks of equal opportunities and freedom for all. She firmly believes that individual freedom should not be gained at the cost of the destruction of other's freedom.

Rama Mehta wants to show that asserting individual freedom at the cost of the peace and harmony of the family is not at all desirable. Sacrifice and reticence are at the very core of happy life. Modernity is not Westernization. It does not lie in being self-centered without caring or bothering for anybody else. The western way of life may bring anxiety, alienation or fragmentation. The true spirit of modernity lies in accepting everyone and everything; forgetting selfish motives; sacrificing for the happiness of others; giving freedom of thought and action to others. This is the essence of Indianness.

Rama Mehta deserves commendation that she does not allow her protagonist to succumb to stagnation or helplessness. Simultaneously, she also keeps her protagonist away from being aggressive, arrogant or outspoken. She is a cultured and dignified woman. Therefore, her heroine Geeta also maintains decorum and self-respect. She does not protest against patriarchy. Becoming a part of the milieu, she succeeds in bringing about a radical change in a sure and subtle manner. By giving respect, she wins one for herself. By bending a bit, she rises high. Her silent revolution is transformative yet respectful of Indian cultural ethos.

Rama Mehta does not equate modernity with Westernization. Geeta's idea of modernity is rooted in education, empathy and consensus; not in blind defiance or isolation. Her relationship with her in-laws and her husband shows that mutual respect and dialogue can bridge generational and cultural gaps. Her in-laws' gradual acceptance of her ideas reveals that change is possible without rupture.

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